

MEASURING OCEAN CURRENTS WITH HF RADAR

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ABSTRACT

HF radar makes it possible to map ocean surface currents from shore without in-situ instruments. Currents are derived from the Doppler shift of echoes from ocean waves a few meters long, whose phase speed is altered by underlying currents. Accuracy of 10 cm/s has been demonstrated with a portable NOAA system called CODAR (Coastal Ocean Dynamics Radar) that illuminates the sea by radio waves that propagate along the ocean surface. With a radar frequency of 25.4 MHz, maps of surface current vectors out to 60 km from shore can be obtained. Longer ranges are possible with lower frequencies, and greater spatial resolution is possible with higher frequencies. Skywave radars, which illuminate the sea by way of ionospheric reflections, have measured ocean currents at much longer ranges (1000-2000 km), but only when very stable ionospheric layers exist, or when nearby stationary targets are available.

Current-mapping radars have already proven useful in several oceanographic research exercises, providing new insights with their graphic displays of transport processes, estuarine flows and tidal oscillations. The CODAR system is now in a Transition Engineering Phase, in which this research tool developed by NOAA is being transformed into an operational instrument with broad scientific and commercial applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Surface currents in the ocean are usually measured with moored current meters or drifting buoys. These methods can be costly and even unsatisfactory if large area coverage (over 1000 km²) with high spatial resolution is required. Now, detailed maps of surface currents are easily obtained with remote-sensing radars that illuminate the sea from the shore or from stationary platforms. These radars can be compact and portable for rapid deployment wherever current measurements are required, and their range can extend to over 100 km from shore.

2. WHY MEASURE SURFACE CURRENTS WITH RADAR?

The current near the ocean surface transports surface-borne pollutants or craft in distress and is

strongly influenced by near-surface meteorology. Furthermore, surface currents can differ considerably in magnitude and direction from currents at depth. Yet, despite their importance, surface currents are difficult to measure with in-situ devices. Current meters moored within several meters of the surface will be influenced by wave action, and surface drifters, which can be costly to deploy and track, respond to wind forces as well as currents.

Shore-based HF radar can measure the currents in the first meter or so below the surface, remotely with no in-situ hardware. Furthermore, it provides a picture of the horizontal spatial structure of the current with a resolution that would require an expensive array of conventional devices to duplicate. Such radar pictures permit a degree of insight never before possible of the surface dynamics of offshore waters.

Six general categories of HF radar applications have been discussed:

1. Oceanographic research — measurements designed to enhance understanding of oceanic physical processes. Examples of such applications would include investigations of sediment transport, coastal and estuarine physics, wave-current interactions and wind-wave generation, propagation and decay.
2. Fisheries management — radar measurements would characterize ocean processes that are critical in the development of yield models and harvesting forecasts for species that spawn offshore but rely on transport inshore to survive. Location of nutrient-rich upwelling zones by HF radar could help determine concentrations of fish stock.
3. Engineering and construction — offshore currents and wave information form design criteria for offshore platforms as well as for piers and jetties. The cost of such structures is inversely related to the quality and quantity of environmental data used in their design.
4. Search and rescue operations — A person and/or craft adrift on the ocean will follow primarily the surface currents, but its trajectory will be deter-

mined also by the wind acting directly on the "sail" area exposed. This "leeway" effect is not fully understood, nor do adequate synoptic surface current files exist for coastal and inland waters.

5. Surveys — the National Ocean Survey of NOAA has a continuing mission to perform surveys of coastal and estuarine circulation in selected U.S. areas. HF radar could greatly simplify the collection of synoptic and climatological current maps for those regions.

6. Environmental assessment — HF radar is ideally suited to support environmental impact assessments and cleanup operations related to offshore oil and hazardous material spills. Synoptic as well as real-time current maps made with HF radar would help in planning and coordinating cleanup and evasive actions at the spill site.

3. HOW HF RADAR MEASURES SEA STATE

Radar echoes from the sea ("sea clutter") have been studied for several decades, but at the microwave frequencies usually used, no straightforward relations have been found between sea-state properties and the echo characteristics. At high frequencies (3-30 MHz), however, the radar waves are much longer and interact with the sea in a way that is relatively easy to model with perturbation theory (Barrick, 1972). This theory says that when HF radar waves backscatter from the sea surface at near-grazing angles, most of the backscattered energy comes from a single component of the ocean-wave spectrum — the waves of one-half the radar wavelength that travel radially toward and away from the radar. This means that out of the crisscrossing and apparently random pattern of waves that makes up the sea surface, an HF radar "selects" the two wave components that most strongly reinforce the backscattered echo.

a. The sea-echo Doppler spectrum

The information that HF radar echoes contain about the sea surface is derived not from the echo's total strength but from its frequency spectrum. Radar echoes from a stationary target return at the same frequency the radar transmitted. But sea echoes are frequency-shifted by the Doppler effect, because the ocean waves they reflect from are moving. The 6-m ocean waves that scatter 25 MHz radar waves, for example, travel at a phase velocity of about 3 m/s. The principal features of a sea-echo Doppler spectrum are therefore two sharp lines with frequency shifts of about ± 0.5 Hz from zero Doppler (at 25 MHz). Because the process that produces these two strong Doppler-shifted lines is similar to the familiar Bragg scattering or diffraction-grating effect, the two spectral lines are usually called the "Bragg lines" in the sea-echo spectrum.

b. Surface-wind and short-wave direction

The relative magnitudes of the positively and negatively shifted Bragg lines indicate the relative strengths of the 6-m ocean waves traveling exactly toward and away from the radar (Crombie, 1955). This ratio can be used to estimate the direction of travel of the strongest 6-m ocean waves and, because these waves are closely coupled to the surface winds, to estimate the surface-wind direction as well. In one example of this application, HF radars using ionospheric reflections have successfully mapped surface-wind-direction fields in tropical storms (Maresca and Carlson, 1980a).

c. Surface currents

The exact frequency shift of the two Bragg lines is a direct measure of the radial velocity of the scattering 6-m waves on the sea surface. In the absence of surface currents, that phase velocity is fixed by the dispersion relation for gravity waves on water, which is known. If surface currents are present, however, the gravity waves are simply transported by the currents, so that the absolute wave speed is the sum of the wave phase velocity and the current component in the direction of wave travel. Therefore, a shift of the two Bragg lines from symmetry about zero Doppler is a direct measure of the radial current component at the location being interrogated (Stewart and Joy, 1974).

An HF radar with suitable range and azimuth resolution can thus map radial current component and wind direction using surface-wave propagation. Two such radars separated by a few tens of kilometers can map current vectors over the region of common coverage (Barrick et al., 1977; Evans and Georges, 1979).

d. Tracking Doppler transponders

Current-sensing HF radars have also demonstrated that they can track floating transponders by using their Doppler-shifted echoes to estimate radial velocity. Doppler transponders can be used to accurately track and detect velocity changes of ships or floating objects (such as ice) without the need for accurate position tracking (Evans et al., 1981). Maximum-entropy spectral analysis permits sampling times to be shortened to 4 seconds or less, permitting accurate tracking during rapid maneuvers.

4. CURRENT-SENSING RADAR SYSTEMS

The most advanced current-sensing HF radar system is the CODAR (Coastal Ocean Dynamics Radar), developed by NOAA as a research tool and now undergoing advanced development aimed at commercial production for operational use (Evans and Georges, 1979; Barrick et al., 1977). CODAR operates in a

frequency range of 25-30 MHz, which gives it a maximum effective range of about 60 km. Lower frequencies tend to give longer ranges because of their lower surface-wave attenuation, but they introduce complications caused by radio-frequency interference and by increased antenna dimensions. Higher (VHF) frequencies would permit the shorter pulse lengths required to achieve greater spatial resolution but the coverage area would be reduced.

At least three other HF surface-wave radar systems are being developed for offshore current measurements. One system, called a Coastal Wave Radar and developed at SRI International, has been demonstrated in an exercise to measure tidal currents in San Francisco Bay (Maresca, et al., 1980).

A research effort in France is a joint project of a government institution (C.N.E.X.O.), oil companies (C.F.P., I.F.P. and S.N.E.A.) and the University of Toulon (I.S.E.E.T.). They have joined efforts to build an operational sea-state radar, a prototype of which was demonstrated in the MARSEN exercise in 1979 (Broche, 1979; DeMaistre et al., 1978).

A third radar is under construction at the University of Northern Queensland, Australia, to measure currents in the vicinity of the Great Barrier Reef (M. Heron, personal communication).

5. HF RADAR ANTENNAS

HF radars are not as common as microwave radars, because the former usually require much larger antennas for comparable angular resolution. Even at 25 MHz, a conventional broadside phased array capable of forming a 5-deg beam would be about 120 m long.

Fortunately, the frequency characteristics of the sea echo permit high angular resolution using very compact phase-measuring antenna arrays. Herein lies the key to a compact, portable current-mapping radar. For example, a four-element array of monopoles developed by the NOAA CODAR team is only 3.5 m on a side, yet it achieves angular resolutions of a fraction of a degree for current-vector mapping (Evans and Georges, 1979). The CODAR receiving array is thus not a conventional phased array; it is instead a phase-measuring array.

6. SIGNAL PROCESSING

The CODAR signal-processing computer performs required Fourier transforms and sorts incoming echoes according to Doppler shift, angle of arrival and range, so that each cell in the radar coverage area is assigned a value of radial current. Data from two radars are combined to produce a current-vector map. Although the total current vector can be directly measured only within the area of common radar coverage, numerical techniques have been developed to extend the vector map beyond the common-coverage area by integrating a two-dimensional continuity equation (Frisch and Leise, 1981). Other

adaptations of the current-mapping processor have been devised to perform sophisticated two-dimensional filtering, for Fourier decomposition of currents into tidal components, for displaying current-map motion pictures, and for computing synthetic drifter tracks.

As the key element of the CODAR system, this signal-processing software has received approximately 70 percent (10-12 man years) of the CODAR development effort. The current-estimating algorithm continues to evolve through stages of increasing output quality, reliability and efficiency. Recent improvements in bookkeeping and efficiency have improved the confidence limits of current estimates by a factor of 10 (from 100 cm/s to 10 cm/s) and have reduced the processing time to nearly that required by a real-time processor.

7. RECENT MEASUREMENTS

The results of a recent field test in the Strait of Juan de Fuca will serve to illustrate CODAR's utility for monitoring estuarine dynamics (Frisch et al., 1981). An offshore storm generated southerly alongshore winds, forcing a surface-current reversal that propagated up the Strait. Figure 1a shows a current map produced by two CODAR stations of the normal outward flow in the Strait. Figure 1b shows a similar map that reveals the complex interaction between seaward and landward flow as the current reversal reached the eastern strait. Each map plots more than 400 current vectors covering a 600-square-kilometer area. The data required to produce each map were averaged over one to three days from archival data, but individual maps can be produced in less than an hour with appropriate on-line processing equipment.

8. MEASUREMENT ACCURACY

A theoretical analysis of the errors inherent in the CODAR hardware/software system predicts a ± 0.1 cm/s probable error in current estimates. Other sources of error dominate the CODAR accuracy estimates. They include second-order hydrodynamic effects that cause deviations from the approximation that currents simply transport ocean waves, and electromagnetic refraction of radar waves near coastlines that can distort the location of radar cells. Such errors are minimized by careful antenna siting and by processing corrections still being refined. The largest source of measurement error is the randomness of the sea surface itself. To reduce the resulting fluctuations in echo amplitude, as well as the effects of external and internal (system) noise, the signal received by the radar must be averaged over time.

Extensive comparisons with current meters and surface drifters have yielded good agreement, the 10-15 percent differences between CODAR and drifter measurements being of the same magnitude as the observed differences between values obtained from initially collocated drifters. The internal consistency of CODAR-derived current fields, the magnitude of their random fluctuations and careful com-

Figure 1. These maps of surface-current vectors in the eastern Strait of Juan de Fuca (Washington) were produced by a pair of HF radars located on the shore at points shown by the asterisks. In (a) a three-day average current map shows the normal seaward (left) flow for summertime. In (b) the 24-hour average map shows the interaction between the outward flow and an eastward-propagating current reversal as it reaches the eastern strait. The dots labeled A, B and C show the locations of moored current meters. Each map shows over 400 current vectors in a 600-km² ocean area. A single (unaveraged) current map with comparable coverage can be produced in about one hour with a real-time processing computer (after Frisch et al., 1981).

comparisons with in-situ devices all point to an accuracy of better than 10 cm/s in CODAR current measurements when radar samples are averaged over one hour.

9. COMPARISON WITH IN-SITU SENSORS

Although radar-derived currents are often "validated" by comparison with in-situ sensors, several difficulties cloud the meaning of such comparisons. First, the calibration and accuracy of "ground-truth" instruments themselves are often not precisely established. Second, point measurements cannot usually be compared with space-time averages, which are complicated by the nonstationarity and inhomogeneity of the ocean surface. Third, small-scale current "turbulence", "averaged out" by radars, can impose large fluctuations on in-situ measurements. (The story is often told of greatly divergent tracks of several drifters deployed simultaneously at the same location.) Because remote and in-situ sensors measure different quantities, it is not usually useful to refer to measurement differences as "errors" in one or the other measurement.

A predisposition toward thinking of established in-situ measurements as "truth", against which radar measurements are to be judged, must also be challenged. Many radar proponents assert that radar is inherently capable of more accurate and useful current measurements than in-situ sensors. In fact, each measurement is a distortion of reality. The assessment of those distortions might better proceed

independently, since the accuracy of HF radar current measurements can be linked to physical "reality" by a chain of reasoning no more complex than that required of in-situ devices. This is not to say, however, that such intercomparisons should not continue, only that care must be taken to configure in-situ sensors to approximate the degree of spatial averaging inherent in radar measurements.

10. CODAR TRANSITION ENGINEERING

To span the gap between prototype and full production, the NOAA Office of Ocean Technology and Engineering Services has initiated a multi-year Transition Engineering Program that will result in the construction of a fully tested and documented CODAR system. Although CODAR has established its value as a research tool in many field tests and in various oceanographic research projects, its availability as a fully operational off-the-shelf instrument is still at least two years away. During that time, detailed engineering and performance specifications must be formulated, and explicit procedures for data collection and interpretation must be standardized. These will be accomplished during the next two years, in which second-generation CODAR systems will be deployed for extended operational tests by selected users. By 1984, we expect a commercial firm to offer production CODAR systems that are simpler, more reliable and more economical than the research instruments now being tested.

11. CURRENT MEASUREMENTS WITH SKYWAVE RADARS

By illuminating the sea and receiving the echo by way of ionospheric reflections, an HF radar can cover ocean areas of millions rather than thousands of square kilometers. The price one pays for the increased coverage of such a skywave or over-the-horizon radar is in the increased cost of larger radar facilities and in distortion of the echo by imperfect ionospheric reflection. Strategies have evolved to overcome this ionospheric distortion, so that surface-wind direction and ocean waveheight can often be mapped with skywave radars (Georges, 1980). But measuring surface currents with skywave radars has proven particularly difficult, because Doppler shifts caused by ionospheric motions are indistinguishable from those caused by ocean currents. Thus, surface currents can be reliably measured with skywave radars only if a stationary target exists in the vicinity of the ocean patch being illuminated. Such a stationary target permits removal of the ionospheric contribution to the Doppler shift, so that the contribution by currents can be identified.

Maresca and Carlson (1980b) have demonstrated long-range measurements of ocean currents near the Gulf Coast using a skywave radar in California, 3000 km away. During the passage of hurricane Anita, long-shore currents induced by the hurricane were measured along the Louisiana coast, using the radar echo from the nearby coastline as a zero-Doppler reference. Radar-derived currents agreed satisfactorily with the measurements by a nearby current meter.

It is not yet known exactly how far from a stationary target currents can be measured, because of the spatial variability of ionospheric motions, but a few tens of kilometers seems to be a maximum when F-layer reflections are used. Ocean currents can be more reliably measured when very stable ionospheric layers, notably sporadic-E layers, exist. D. Trizna at the Naval Research Laboratory (1981) has measured Gulf Stream currents in this way, but little is yet known about the frequency shifts and spatial stability of sporadic-E reflections.

12. REFERENCES

- Barrick, D.E., Remote sensing of sea state by radar, Remote Sensing of the Troposphere, V.E. Derr, Ed., Ch. 12, U.S. Govt. Printing Off., Washington, DC, 1972.
- Barrick, D.E., M.W. Evans and B.L. Weber, Ocean surface currents mapped by radar, Science **198**, 138-144, 1977.
- Broche, P., Sea-state directional spectra observed by HF Doppler radar, AGARD Conference Proceedings No. 263, Paper No. 31, 1979.
- Crombie, D.D., Doppler spectrum of sea echo at 13.56 Mc/s, Nature **175**, 681-682, 1955.
- DeMaistre, J.C., P. Broche and M. Crocket, Off-shore wind measurements by HF Doppler ground-wave radar, Boundary Layer Meteorology **13**, 55-60, 1978.
- Evans, M.W. and T.M. Georges, Coastal Ocean Dynamics Radar (CODAR): NOAA's surface current mapping system, Proc. Oceans '79 Conference, IEEE, 379-384, 1979.
- Evans, M.W., T.M. Georges and B.L. Weber, Tracking the velocity and position of offshore vessels and floating objects with HF Doppler transponders, IEEE Jour. Oceanic Engr. **OE-6**, 1-4, 1981.
- Frisch, A.S., J. Holbrook and A.B. Ages, Observations of a summertime reversal in the circulation in the Strait of Juan de Fuca, J. Geophys. Res. **86C3**, 2044-2048, 1981.
- Frisch, A.S. and J. Leise, Using continuity to extend HF radar surface-current measurements, J. Geophys. Res. (in press) 1981.
- Georges, T.M., Progress toward a practical skywave sea-state radar, IEEE Trans. Antennas and Propagation, **AP-28**, 751-761, 1980.
- Maresca, J.W., Jr., High-frequency radar measurements of tidal currents flowing through San Pablo Strait, San Francisco Bay, Limnol. Oceanogr. **25**, 929-935, 1980.
- Maresca, J.W., Jr. and C.T. Carlson, High-frequency skywave radar measurements of hurricane Anita, Science **209**, 1189-1196, 1980a.
- Maresca, J.W., Jr., and C.T. Carlson, Comment on 'longshore currents on the fringe of Hurricane Anita' by Ned P. Smith, J. Geophys. Res. **85C3**, 1640-1641, 1980b.
- Stewart, R.H. and J.W. Joy, HF radio measurements of ocean surface currents, Deep Sea Res. **21**, 1039-1049, 1974.
- Trizna, D.B., Preliminary results on mapping ocean currents with over-the-horizon radar, Paper presented at URSI meeting, Boulder, CO, January 1981.